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THESIS OUTLINE

TITLE: The Maritime Cities of the Persian Gulf and their Commercial
Role from the 5th Century to 1507.

Section I: Introduction

- Chapter 1. The problems of the maritime cities.
- Chapter 2. Sources and methods of research.
- Chapter 3. The Geographical background.
- Chapter 4. The historical background.

Section II: History

- Chapter 5. Rīshahr and the development of trade from the 3rd to the 7th centuries A.D..
- Chapter 6. The origins of direct maritime trade with the Far East.
- Chapter 7. Sīrāf and Abbāsīd trade, 800-1100 A.D..
- Chapter 8. Kīsh and Hurmuz, rivals in the Gulf, 1100-1500 A.D..
- Chapter 9. Hurmuz and the trade of the Gulf in the 14th and 15th centuries A.D..

Section III: Analysis

- Chapter 10. The items of trade
 - a. East African and South Arabian.
 - b. Indian and Far Eastern.
 - c. Western.
 - d. Local products.
- Chapter 11. Transport and mechanical factors of trade.
- Chapter 12. Markets and organization of trade.
- Chapter 13. The theory of the entrepôt.
- Chapter 14. The role of the maritime cities in the trade of Asia.

APPENDIX I. Diagnostic pottery types.

APPENDIX II. Archaeological evidence for settlement distribution.

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